

1. Introduction

The InspectionGate system is a highly innovative smart inspection tool for the commercial aerospace industry. It helps airlines & MROs reduce maintenance time and cost by making aircraft skin inspections radically faster, more reliable, and better documented with a cutting-edge solution.

Our mission is to give a hand to maintenance engineers through digital technologies to avoid manual and paper-heavy operations, such as damage recognition and localization. Using the InspectionGate solution, inspectors and system users can eliminate misunderstandings and speed up their inspection processes.

This document aims to detail the usage of the InspectionGate system. It contains guidance and clarification for users regarding the InspectionGate workflow and functionalities.

2. InspectionGate System Overview

In this chapter we overview the basic concept and architecture of the InspectionGate System.

2.1 What is the InspectionGate System?

InspectionGate is a supporting tool for aerospace engineers. The system provides instant information about exterior damages during the aircraft skin inspection process. Users can use the Gate to automatically generate high-quality photos of the aircraft exterior to perform the skin inspection process digitally, much faster and easier, potentially even remotely. With the help of real-time data flow, users can access the previously recorded data immediately at their workstation and perform further actions such as damage registration, data correction, damage assessment, or reporting.

2.2 What purpose does it serve?

Today's highly developed technological environment makes it possible to increase efficiency through digitized solutions. We aim to support users in making the right decision as quickly as possible and shortening long hours spent detecting and documenting damage location and data. Our purpose is to ease and speed up everyday operations to determine aircraft go/no-go decisions much more rapidly.

With our system, the aircraft status is instantly available in our database, which means a direct pipeline of information between parties like the engineer, MRO, operator, owner, lessor, and manufacturer. Being connected to the same data network increases the traceability of the aircraft status, informing the authorized persons about the details of a planned maintenance results in real-time.

2.3 Who uses it and when?

The InspectionGate system can be used for both:

- Line Maintenance
- Base (Heavy) Maintenance

Aircraft engineers can use the system to:

- Re-examine previously registered damages during an inspection by the aircraft
- Identify and register new damages during an inspection by the aircraft
- Generate reports

Management can use the system to:

- Browse, search, or export aircraft damage data
- Monitor the status of inspections
- Monitor the performance of engineers and technicians
- Generate reports

The system can also be used by aircraft owners, lessors, operators, airlines, or manufacturers to monitor the status of inspections and receive up-to-date, accurate, and detailed damage data.

2.4 System Architecture

The InspectionGate System consists of closely related components:

- The **InspectionGate** is the hardware that performs an automated aircraft skin inspection, generating photos of the aircraft exterior.
- The **PostProcessing** component is responsible for generating the meta-data to the recorded photos which is necessary for interpretation and structured storage.
- The **InspectionGate Windows Application** (running on Windows 10 based PC, laptop, or tablet) is used by engineers, technicians, and managers. Users can control the InspectionGate (hardware) to start and stop inspection processes, then view, browse, and search the gathered visual data, and generate reports.
- Both the **InspectionGate** and the **InspectionGate Windows Application** communicate with the **InspectionGate Backend Server**, which is responsible for storing, synchronizing, and retrieving the collected and maintained data.
- The shared backend server enables the communication between components to ensure that data is in sync in the other components, and newly recorded data is instantly visible to other users sitting in the office or on the other side of the world.

3. General System Features

In this chapter we overview the general features and functions of the InspectionGate System.

3.1 User Interface (UI)

The system's menu bar is located on the left side of the screen with its essential menus. These are the following ones:

- **Manage Inspections:** users can control the InspectionGate in this menu
- **Inspection Results:** users can view, browse and search data recorded during inspections
- **Aircrafts:** maintenance of inspected aircrafts and their base data
- **Admin:** A menu with sub-menus to supply system operation
- **User Profile:** users can reach their base data here, including the capability of password modification
- **Logout:** by pressing it, users log out from the InspectionGate Windows Application
- **Info:** Information about InspectionGate Support

Generally, menu-specific toolbars, filters, etc. are located on the top of the screen. Editable data can be found on a panel on the right side of the screen, along with Save and Cancel buttons. Last but not least, data visualization with charts, 3D aircraft models, and other displaying tools are on the middle part of the screen.

Furthermore, the footer at the bottom gives you information as regards system version data such as User, Client Version, Server Version, Database, and Environment. This information can be useful when contacting InspectionGate support.

If you intended to export data, you need to click on the Excel Export button placed on the top right corner of a window or panel. The export button can be found on every screen and panel where data exporting comes into consideration.

On the top right corner of the screens, you can find the Refresh button. System-wide operation based on manual refreshing! The function updates all events that had happened in the system since your latest login or refresh. After the refresh, you will stay on the same screen where you were, you will not be redirected elsewhere.

To register, modify or delete data in the InspectionGate system, you should always confirm your changes with the Save button. During the confirmation, the system runs validation tests to check that the new or modified data meet the determined formal and substantive requirements. If it does not meet the established rules, a pop-up window will notify you what had exactly gone wrong, and you should revise your changes.

To handle tables in the InspectionGate Windows Application, you can use scroll bars, and you have the chance also to sort data according to columns. For this, you should click on the name on a column.

3.2 Authentication

To access the system functions, the users must authenticate themselves when logging in to the InspectionGate system. This process achieves three main goals:

- The system does not provide access for individuals who do not have the required authorization.
- Each individual can only use the system in their name, not on behalf of others.
- Individuals have access only to the functions they were authorized to use.

Currently, the system handles the **username and password combination based authentication**:

- Users log in by typing their username and password combination
- The system administrator can create and update each user's username and password in the InspectionGate Windows Application
- Users can also change their password in the application

3.3 User Management and Permissions

User management and permission handling are robust in the InspectionGate System. Controlling and monitoring user access is a fundamental security cornerstone of an organization and its system components.

- System administrators can define distinct access levels by assigning privileges to Roles.
- Roles are made up of separate functions, allowing for granular access control.
- User access is inherited through the assigned Roles.
- Individual privileges cannot be directly assigned to a User.
- Users can have multiple Roles assigned to them, inheriting all allowed privileges from their Roles

3.4 Activity Logging

The InspectionGate System stores every event to log files with diverse data sets. It can handle different time zones, enabling users to set their time zone preferences.

The distinct logging structures and their purposes are the followings:

- **Custom business logging:** Each function has a corresponding and distinct log element. These have a uniquely defined structure for the associated entity and its functions. Using a function generates a unique log event entry.
- **Global business logging** (accessible by administrator users through the InspectionGate Windows Application): The global business log is available in the “System Log” menu item, which logs all events in the system in a unified structure. All log elements are saved in the system database.

3.5 Error Handling

Error handling refers to the response and recovery procedures from error conditions present in the InspectionGate system. It helps to maintain the normal flow of system operation.

The system logs the following types of errors in the error log:

- **Unhandled exceptions** are instances when the system is not able to execute a specific task. The system notifies the user of these occurrences through appropriate, interpretable error messages.
- **Faults** are unexpected and unhandled occurrences that require an additional operator or developer intervention. Example: communication faults between components.

Errors are automatically logged in the following error log:

- **Global error log** (accessible by administrator users through the InspectionGate Windows Application): The list of errors that occurred in the system is available in the “Error log” menu with a uniform structure.

4. Admin Functions

Admin menu and the belonging sub-menus should be available only for users who own system administrator roles. By hovering the mouse cursor on the menu icon, sub-menus will appear and become eligible to open.

4.1 Aircrafts

What is this menu for?

In Aircrafts Menu, you can maintain the list of registered aircrafts and their basic information.

Why is it needed?

To execute the InspectionGate inspection process, it needs to register the specific aircraft into the System.

Who is using it and when?

You can use this menu to add, modify and delete aircrafts that have been inspected or still waiting for it.

How does it work?

In case of an aircraft addition, you should click on the New Aircraft button and fill out Aircraft data then closing it with the Save button or interrupt the process with the Cancel button. You have the opportunity to edit aircraft data if some of them have changed. To execute data modification, you have to select the aircraft, click on Modify Aircraft button, and edit the necessary data. To delete an aircraft from the list, you should click on the Delete Aircraft button and confirm your decision on the appearing pop-up window.

Editable aircraft data fields are (*required field):

- **Registration number***: The registration number of the aircraft
- **Manufacturer serial number***: The manufacturer serial number of the aircraft
- **Aircraft type***: The type of the aircraft
- **Weight variant**: The weight variant of the aircraft.
- **Customer***: Name of the customer

- **Description:** Field for further notes regarding the aircraft

4.2 Admin / Aircraft Types

The screenshot displays the 'AIRCRAFT TYPES' menu in the InspectionGate Smart Inspection - Development application. The main window shows a table of aircraft types with columns for CODE, NAME, MANUFACTURER, AIRCRAFT FAMILY, MEASUREMENT UNIT, AIRCRAFT MODEL NAME, SRM AIRCRAFT TYPE, and DESCRIPTION. The table lists four entries for Airbus A320 Family aircraft.

CODE	NAME	MANUFACTURER	AIRCRAFT FAMILY	MEASUREMENT UNIT	AIRCRAFT MODEL NAME	SRM AIRCRAFT TYPE	DESCRIPTION
A318	A318	Airbus	Airbus A320 Family	Metric units (mm)	A318	A318 - ST4	
A319	A319	Airbus	Airbus A320 Family	Metric units (mm)	A319	A319 - ST3	
A320	A320	Airbus	Airbus A320 Family	Metric units (mm)	A320	A320 - ST1	
A321	A321	Airbus	Airbus A320 Family	Metric units (mm)	A321	A321 - ST2	

To the right of the table is the 'AIRCRAFT TYPE DATA' form, which displays the details for the selected aircraft type (A318). The form fields are:

- CODE: A318
- NAME: A318
- MANUFACTURER: Airbus
- AIRCRAFT FAMILY: Airbus A320 Family
- MEASUREMENT UNIT: Metric units (mm)
- AIRCRAFT MODEL NAME: A318
- SRM AIRCRAFT TYPE: A318 - ST4
- DESCRIPTION: (empty field)

The application interface includes a sidebar with navigation icons for Manage, Inspection methods, AIRCRAFTS, ADMIN, SET TOOLS, USER PROFILE, LOGOUT, and INFO. The status bar at the bottom shows: User: Zoltán Wéber, Client version: 1.0.0.0, Server version: 1.0.0.0, Database: Inspectiongate/InspectionGate, Environment: Development.

What is this menu for?

Aircraft Types menu is a read-only screen, where you can see the different aircraft types with their primary data handled by our system.

Why is it needed?

It informs you of the currently supported aircraft types.

Who is using it and when?

Generally, you use this screen to inform yourself and your colleagues of the currently supported aircraft models and their primary data.

How does it work?

Aircraft Types menu includes the following data from the aircrafts:

- **Code**
- **Name**
- **Manufacturer:** Name of the manufacturer who built the aircraft.
- **Aircraft family:** Name of the aircraft family the aircraft belongs.
- **Measurement unit:** The default measurement unit of an aircraft type (inch or mm)
- **Aircraft model name**
- **SRM aircraft type:** Name of the aircraft type based on the SRM appellation
- **Description:** Field for further notes regarding the aircraft type

4.3 Admin / Customers

What is this menu for?

Here, you can maintain the customer list and its main information.

Why is it needed?

It enables you to add new customers to the system or modify existing ones' data.

Who is using it and when?

Aircraft cannot be registered without its customer. With system administrator rights, you should add or modify the inspectable aircraft's customer data if it does not exist or has changed to keep data up to date.

How does it work?

You can handle determined functions on the screen by clicking on New Customer, Modify User or Delete Customer buttons. If a customer has been assigned to an aircraft, you will not be able to delete it.

Customers contain the following fields:

- **Short name:** Abbreviation of the customer's name
- **Full name:** Customer's entire name
- **Description:** Field for further notes regarding the customer

4.4 Admin / Users

The screenshot displays the 'InspectionGate Smart Inspection - Development' application. The main window is titled 'USERS' and contains a table with the following data:

DOMAIN	USERNAME	DISPLAYED NAME	E-MAIL ADDRESS	QR CODE	BARCODE	RECEIVE NOTIFICATIONS	ACTIVE	R
gate	inspectiongate	Technical User	support@inspectiongate.com			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Min
gate	janos.coordas	János Coördás	7			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Min
gate	laszlo.gonda	László Gonda	6			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Min
gate	test	Test User	3			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Min
gate	zoltan.weber	Zoltán Weber	1			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	WZ

Below the table, there are buttons for 'NEW USER', 'MODIFY USER', 'DELETE USER', and 'CHANGE PASSWORD'. To the right, the 'USER DATA' form is visible, showing fields for 'DOMAIN', 'USERNAME', 'DISPLAYED NAME', 'E-MAIL ADDRESS', 'QR CODE', 'BARCODE', 'RECEIVE NOTIFICATION', and 'ACTIVE'. Below the form, there is a 'ROLES' section with checkboxes for 'Minden jog' and 'WZ test'.

What is this menu for?

User management is a vital part of the system as each user's data are managed on this screen, and user accounts will operate according to the settings maintained here. First and foremost, you can add users and set up their accounts here to use the system. Different users may use other parts of the system. Therefore, you need to define personalized responsibilities per user to ensure safe operation; each individual has access only for his/her entitled functions.

Why is it needed?

It aims to add/modify/delete users or add/remove their roles easily and quickly without external help.

Who is using it and when?

You can use this screen as a system administrator in those cases when you have to add a new user to the system or modify/disable an existing user's data, settings, and roles.

How does it work?

You can add users and fill out their data by clicking on the New User button. To execute other operations on the screen, you have to select the exact user as a first step; then, you can click on the appropriate function button. You can close user management activity by clicking on Save or Cancel button.

The following functionalities are available on the user management screen:

- **New User:** By clicking this button, you can add a new user to the system.
- **Modify User:** You can modify a user's base data, password, and role.
- **Delete User:** This function deletes a selected user from the system. Deletion can be confirmed in the appearing pop-up window.
- **Change Password:** You can change other users' passwords.

The following user data can be edited:

- **Domain:** Name of your company

- **Username:** This name should be entered during the login session to authenticate yourself
- **Displayed Name:** This name will be displayed in the system
- **E-mail Address:** Your company-related e-mail address must be added here to be able to get notifications via e-mail regarding system activities
- **Receive Notifications:** Users with a green tick have the right to get notifications from system-related activities via e-mail.
- **Active:** Active users (green tick) can use InspectionGate System as stated in their role. However, deactivated users (without a tick) would not be able to use it and log into the system until they have not reclaimed their Active status.
- **Roles:** A role is a component that consists of the desired privileges and determines which functions the user can use. Ticking a role's box means you added a role with its privilege set to a user.

4.5 Admin / Roles

What is this menu for?

Here, you can maintain user roles with their unique privilege set.

Why is it needed?

You can use the InspectionGate System based on your role (user rights). The list of functions you can reach depends on what kind of privilege set had been added to an exact role.

Roles are designed to create sets of privileges that you can then assign to multiple users. However, without them, you would always have to tick privileges one by one. Changing a role also updates the privileges of all connected users. You can easily set these tasks without external intervention.

Who is using it and when?

You can use this screen to add, modify, delete roles, and assign or take away privileges as a system administrator.

How does it work?

You can Add, Modify, or Delete user roles by clicking on the proper button on the screen's top-left corner.

To modify or delete a role, you have to select one as a first step; then, you can edit data or confirm your intention to delete the role in a pop-up window. In case of a new role addition or existing role modification, you have to Save changes as a final step. However, if you have changed your mind, the process can be easily dismissed with the Cancel button.

Editable data of a role are:

- **Name:** Displayed name of a role
- **AD Group:** If you are a member of an existing Active Directory (AD) Group, you will automatically get the group's roles with its belonging privileges. This functionality is currently in the development pipeline.
- **Description:** Field for further notes regarding the role. Added text will appear on the user detail panel if you hover the mouse pointer on a role.
- **Privileges:** Privileges determine the accessible functions for a user and can be gathered in a role to handle them as a group. You can assign them one by one to a role. The list of privileges is fixed; only new developments can change it.

4.6 Admin / System Log

EVENT DATE	ACTOR USER	ALIAS USER	SYSTEM COMPONENT	CLIENT INFORMATION	EVENT TYPE	ENTITY TYPE	ENTITY ID	ENTITY NAME
06.04.2022 19:27:39	Zoltán Wéber	Zoltán Wéber	InspectionGate Windows Application	176.63.14.12	Login / Username-Password	User	5d158648-239c-4fb9-8f83-0b87493e882	Zoltán Wéber(gate)\zolta
06.04.2022 18:28:23	Zoltán Wéber	Zoltán Wéber	InspectionGate Windows Application	176.63.14.12	Login / Username-Password	User	5d158648-239c-4fb9-8f83-0b87493e882	Zoltán Wéber(gate)\zolta
04.04.2022 15:43:00	Zoltán Wéber	Zoltán Wéber	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.99.11.225	Login / Username-Password	User	5d158648-239c-4fb9-8f83-0b87493e882	Zoltán Wéber(gate)\zolta
04.04.2022 15:35:33	János Csordás	János Csordás	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.99.11.225	Modify	Inspection Data	e3d0f85-ff62-47be-919a-94c4350c7191	AY-565 - #2
04.04.2022 15:33:00	János Csordás	János Csordás	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.99.11.225	Stop	Inspection	59795006-ac17-45b7-bc12-825ca44b3d18	AA-111 - #2

What is this menu for?

The system's central log records user activities to monitor operation, interfere in case of necessity and correct inappropriately recorded data or commands.

Why is it needed?

Using this menu, you can supply an inspection's control without operator/developer intervention and respond immediately respecting the arising issues.

Who is using it and when?

As a system administrator, you can use this menu to monitor employees' activities or look for answers regarding the occurring questions and problems.

How does it work?

You can find any event and the related information that occurred in the past on the read-only screen. To look after an actual event, you should scroll and use the pager by clicking on the arrows. With pagers, you can jump to the next/previous or first/last pages.

If you want to decrease the log entries list or look for something special, you can filter according to each column type of the screen or a combination of them. To execute filtering, you have to click on the Query button.

Columns/Filtering options are the following elements:

- **Event Date From:** Start date of your filtering interval. This day's log items will be the earliest ones in your filtered list
- **Event Date To:** End date of your filtering interval. This day's log items will be the ones in your filtered list
- **Actor User:** The user who executes the activity in the system
- **Alias User:** This functionality is currently in the development pipeline.
- **System Component:** This column shows you on which component occurred the activity (InspectionGate Windows Application, or InspectionGate Backend)
- **Client Information:** The IP address where the executed activity occurred
- **Event Type:** The type of an event that you made in the system, f.e. modify, login, etc.
- **Entity Type:** The type of the entity on which you made the activity
- **Entity Name:** Name of the entity on which you made the activity
- **Description:** More exact explanation of the event

In the system log list, log entries are sorted chronologically decreasing order by default; of course, you can customize this. In the columns of the chart, you can find the data of the events. Data cannot be modified; it is only available in read-only mode. That is the reason for the lack of action buttons.

4.7 Admin / Error Log

The screenshot displays the 'InspectionGate Smart Inspection - Development' application window. The main content area is titled 'ERROR LOG' and features a table of error entries. Above the table is a 'FILTERS' section with various input fields and a 'QUERY' button. The table columns are: EVENT DATE, ACTOR USER, SYSTEM COMPONENT, CLIENT INFORMATION, ERROR LEVEL, and GENERATED ERRORMESSAGE. The error messages include details about exceptions and resource not found errors.

EVENT DATE	ACTOR USER	SYSTEM COMPONENT	CLIENT INFORMATION	ERROR LEVEL	GENERATED ERRORMESSAGE
06.01.2022 15:06:17	Test User	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.98.133.167	Error	'Provide value on 'System.Windows.Baml2006.TypeConverterMarkupExtension' threw an exception.' Line number '9' and line pos
06.01.2022 15:06:16	Test User	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.98.133.167	Error	'Provide value on 'System.Windows.Baml2006.TypeConverterMarkupExtension' threw an exception.' Line number '9' and line pos
06.01.2022 15:06:13	Test User	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.98.133.167	Error	Exception has been thrown by the target of an invocation.
06.01.2022 15:05:58	Test User	InspectionGate Windows Application	80.98.133.167	Error	Value cannot be null. Parameter name: path3
14.05.2021 09:19:19	Test User	InspectionGate Windows Application	194.143.233.166	Error	'DamagesDataGridCellElement' resource not found.

What is this menu for?

The system's central error log lists all the errors that occurred in the InspectionGate System.

Why is it needed?

This menu gathers the occurring system-related errors and provides information to solve them.

Who is using it and when?

This menu is used by the InspectionGate team to identify and troubleshoot arising system errors. However, you can also reach this menu and send the exported error log to InspectionGate Support in case of necessity.

How does it work?

You can find any error event and related information that occurred in the past on the read-only screen. To look after an actual error event, you can scroll and use the pager by clicking on the arrows. With pagers, you can jump to the next/previous or first/last pages. If you want to decrease the list of the log entries, you can filter according to each column type of the screen or combination of them. To execute filtering, you have to click on the Query button.

Columns/Filtering options are the following elements:

- **Event Date From:** Start date of your filtering interval. This day's log items will be the earliest ones in your filtered list
- **Event Date To:** End date of your filtering interval. This day's log items will be the latest ones in your filtered list
- **Actor User:** The user who evoke the error in the system
- **System Component:** This column shows you on which component occurred the error (InspectionGate Windows Application or InspectionGate Backend)
- **Client Information:** The IP address on which device the error occurred
- **Error Level**
- **Generated Error Message:** Short description of the error
- **Automatic Error Message**
- **Stack Trace:** Detailed description of the error

In the error log list, log entries are sorted chronologically decreasing order by default; of course, you can customize this. Data cannot be modified; it is only available in read-only mode. That is the reason for the lack of action buttons.

4.8 Admin / System Parameter

PARAMETER CODE	PARAMETER VALUE	DESCRIPTION
ApplicationName	Inspection Gate Windows Application	The name of the Inspection Gate Windows Application
Environment	Development	The environment of the system (Development, Test, Production, etc.)
ExcelExportLimit	500	The record limit in Excel export (beyond the limit a confirmation is presented)
Gate_MaxPosition_mm	8000	Maximum position (in mm) of the gate along the SRM X axis
Gate_MinPosition_mm	400	Minimum position (in mm) of the gate along the SRM X axis
Gate_PositionInterval_mm	250	Maximum position (in mm) of the gate along the SRM X axis
JwtTokenExpMinWindowsApp	30	Api token expiration time in minutes in the Inspection Gate Windows Application
LockTimeMin	30	Entity locking time in minutes
LoginPasswordNeeded	0	Password needed for login (1 = TRUE, 0 = FALSE)
MaintenanceProvider	Gate Inspection Ltd.	Maintenance Service Provider Company Name
RefreshTokenExpMin	1440	Refresh token expiration time in minutes
Station	KEC	Default station of the service provider
UserSettings_LoadEnabled	1	User settings are loaded and used in the Inspection Gate System
UserSettings_SaveEnabled	1	User settings are saved and constantly updated in the Inspection Gate System
WindowsApp_GridPageSize	50	The number of records in one page in the pagged data grids in Inspection Gate Windows Application

What is this menu for?

System parameters are used to adjust key operation settings. With the help of these elements, basic parameters can be customized.

Why is it needed?

System parameters are responsible for basic system configuration. To keep the InspectionGate System flexible, it is necessary to evolve these kinds of parameters.

Who is using it and when?

The InspectionGate Support Team is the responsible party to determine these parameters to ensure the proper operation of its partners.

4.9 User Profile

DOMAIN	gate
USERNAME	zoltan.weber
DISPLAYED NAME	Zoltán Weber
E-MAIL ADDRESS	1
RECEIVE NOTIFICATION	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTIVE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
CURRENT PASSWORD *	*****
NEW PASSWORD *	*****
CONFIRM NEW PASSWORD *	*****

[CHANGE PASSWORD](#)

The User Profile contains the details and settings of the logged in user, listing:

- Domain
- Username

- Displayed name
- E-mail address
- Receive notification
- Active

Users can change their password by filling in the Current Password and filling in the New Password and Confirm New Password fields, then clicking on the Change Password button.

4.10 Info Menu

The Info Menu contains the channel to contact the InspectionGate Team.

5. Managing Inspections

AIRCRAFT	INSPECTION NUMBER	START DATE	END DATE	STATUS	START POSITION (mm)	END POSITION (mm)	POSITION INTERVAL (mm)	CAMERA CONFIGURATION	DESCRIPTION	ERROR	NUMBER OF PHOTOS
AA-111	2	04.04.2022 15:32:51	04.04.2022 15:33:00	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	10	06.03.2022 15:17:32	04.04.2022 15:32:26	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	9	03.06.2021 12:43:00	06.03.2022 15:17:08	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
BZ-356	4	13.05.2021 18:33:24	14.05.2021 14:21:39	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AA-111	1	11.05.2021 10:46:50	06.03.2022 15:16:58	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	8	11.05.2021 10:43:31	03.06.2021 12:42:48	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	7	06.05.2021 18:37:51	06.05.2021 18:44:44	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	6	06.05.2021 18:25:37	06.05.2021 18:37:43	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
AY-565	4	22.04.2021 14:46:52	27.04.2021 08:45:36	Stopped	400	8000	250				0
BZ-356	1	22.04.2021 13:23:10	22.04.2021 13:26:24	Finished	0	80020	250				0
AY-565	2	22.04.2021 13:20:19	22.04.2021 13:21:19	Error	0	10000	250	wqewq	sadwqeeq	asdasdda	44
AY-565	1	22.04.2021 13:15:40	22.04.2021 13:20:03	Stopped	0	8000	250				0

What is this menu for?

In the Manage Inspections Menu, you can control and follow the status of the InspectionGate (hardware) to perform automated gate inspections.

Why is it needed?

To execute the InspectionGate inspection process, a User Interface is needed to control the Gate and the inspection process.

Who is using it and when?

An aircraft engineer standing near the InspectionGate uses this functionality, when an automated inspection needs to be performed.

How does it work?

You can control the inspection gate with three separate commands:

Start New Inspection
✕

AIRCRAFT

AV-565

A320

123458

Cust #1

START POSITION (mm)
400

END POSITION (mm)
8000

POSITION INTERVAL (mm)
250

DESCRIPTION

CREATE AND START

CANCEL

- **New Inspection function:** with this function you can start a new inspection process. First you have to set up its parameters on a popup window (see screenshot above)
- **Stop Inspection function:** with this function you can stop and ongoing (In progress) inspection process and reset the InspectionGate to its initial state and position
- **Delete Inspection function:** with this function you can delete an already finished inspection process when you don't need its data anymore

At the main area of the screen you see the list of inspections related to particular aircrafts. The presented fields of an inspection process are the following:

- **Aircraft:** Registration number of the aircraft that the inspection is or was performed on
- **Inspection number:** the automatically generated (integer) identifier number of an inspection within a given aircraft
- **Start date:** exact start date and time of the inspection process
- **End date:** exact end date and time of the inspection process
- **Status:** status of the inspection process (In progress / Error / Stopped / Finished / Stopping)
- **Start position (mm):** start position of the InspectionGate at the start of the inspection
- **End position (mm):** end position of the InspectionGate at the end of the inspection
- **Position interval (mm):** intervals of data recordings between the start and the end position
- **Camera configuration:** configuration data of the InspectionGate cameras
- **Description:** field for further notes regarding the specific inspection
- **Error:** generated error message of the InspectionGate in case an error happened
- **Number of photos:** number of photos recorded during the inspection

During an ongoing inspection process you can receive up-to-date information about the inspection's status and the number of photos recorded by pressing the **Refresh** button at the top-left corner of the screen.

6. Inspection Results

What is this menu for?

In the Inspection Results Menu, you can view, browse and search the inspection data generated by the InspectionGate during an automated inspection.

Why is it needed?

This menu item and functionality is needed to be able to interpret and easily and quickly navigate through the hundreds and thousands of photos recorded during the inspection.

Who is using it and when?

Aircraft engineers use this function when they want to process the results of an inspection for damage identification, registration, and assessment.

How does it work?

The screen is divided into the following parts:

- **Header top row:** aircraft selection, inspection selection, and refresh button
- **Header bottom row:** with inspection data (recorded photo) selection, filters, and data modify button
- **Inspection Data on Aircraft:** 3D visualization of the virtual aircraft with the inspection data (recorded photos) visualized on it
- **Inspection Data List:** show an entire list of inspection data of the selected aircraft inspection
- **Inspection Data Details:** panel with detailed overview of one selected inspection data (recorded photo and its meta-data)

During an ongoing inspection process you can receive up-to-date information about the inspection data generated by pressing the **Refresh** button at the top-left corner of the screen.

6.1 Header Controls

The header's top row contains the aircraft selector combo box. After selecting the aircraft to work with, you can select different inspections with the inspection selector combo box.

In the bottom row you can select inspection data by ID or page between first, previous, next, and last. Also you can filter the presented damages.

6.2 Inspection Data on Aircraft

Here, you can see the virtual 3D aircraft model which is the digital twin version of the real physical aircraft that was inspected.

Some buttons will help you move the 3D model into several positions on the left side of the panel. To learn how to handle further movements, press the information (i) icon on the top right corner. Through navigation and keyboard shortcuts, you acquire the complete handling of the virtual aircraft.

In the header of the Inspection Data on Aircraft Panel there are a few configuration check boxes:

- Show frames/stringers: shows and hides the structural elements of the aircraft like frames and stringers
- Jump to selected inspection data: if this is checked then the system will always jump to a camera location from where the photo was recorded when you select an inspection data
- Show thumbnails: visualizes the small versions of the photos taken on the actual location of the recordings on the surface of the aircraft

6.3 Inspection Data List

INSPECTION DATA LIST												
Data ID	Gate Position (mm)	Camera ID	Camera Position X (mm)	Camera Position Y (mm)	Camera Position Z (mm)	Camera Orientation X	Camera Orientation Y	Camera Orientation Z	Focus Distance (mm)	Horizontal Field of View	Vertical Field of View	Shutter Ti
1	1	1	8400	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
2	2	1	9200	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
3	3	1	10000	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
4	4	1	10800	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
5	5	1	11600	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
6	6	1	12400	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
7	7	1	13200	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
8	8	1	14000	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
9	9	1	14800	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
10	10	1	15600	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
11	11	1	16400	863	3126	-863	-3222	1	40	57	1	
12	12	2	8400	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
13	13	2	9200	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
14	14	2	10000	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
15	15	2	10800	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
16	16	2	11600	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
17	17	2	12400	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
18	18	2	13200	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	
19	19	2	14000	2888	1572	-2888	-1668	1	40	57	1	

At the main area of the screen you see the list of inspection data recorded during the selected inspection with the following meta-data:

- **Data ID:** unique integer identifier of the inspection data within an inspection
- **Gate Position (mm):** the position of the gate when the data was recorded
- **Camera ID:** unique identifier of the camera that recorded the data
- **Camera position X / Y / Z (mm):** the official SRM-based coordinates of the camera that recorded the data at the time of the recording
- **Camera orientation X / Y / Z:** the 3D orientation coordinates of the camera that recorded the data at the time of the recording
- **Focus distance (mm):** focus distance of the camera in mm at the time of the recording
- **Horizontal / Vertical Field of View:** horizontal / vertical field of view of the camera in degrees
- **Shutter time:** shutter time of the camera
- **Folder name:** name of the folder where the actual photo is stored
- **Filename:** name of the file in which the photo is stored
- **File extension:** extension of the file in which the photo is stored
- **File size (kB):** file size of the photo in kilobytes
- **Comment:** comment attached to the photo by a user
- **Creation date:** exact date and time when the photo was recorded

6.4 Inspection Data Details

On the right side of the screen you find a panel with all the details of the selected inspection data consisting of the actual photo and the meta-data.

In the upper part the photo is displayed with the following options:

- Zoom in and out
- Move the photo around with the mouse
- Open the photo in the default picture viewer application
- Save the photo to the local computer

In the bottom part the same meta-data is displayed as in the table-view (Inspection Data List part of the screen), in different field groups:

EDITABLE DATA	
COMMENT	ez nem egy comment

INSPECTION DATA		CAMERA DATA	
AIRCRAFT	AY-565	CAMERA ID	2
INSPECTION	AY-565 - #2	CAMERA POSITION X (mm)	9200
BASE DATA		CAMERA POSITION Y (mm)	2888
DATA ID	13	CAMERA POSITION Z (mm)	1572
CREATION DATE	26.05.2021 15:22:29	CAMERA ORIENTATION X	
GATE POSITION (mm)	13	CAMERA ORIENTATION Y	-2888
RELATED FILE DATA		CAMERA ORIENTATION Z	-1668
FOLDER NAME	x	FOCUS DISTANCE (mm)	1
FILENAME	13	HORIZONTAL FIELD OF VIEW	40
FILE EXTENSION	jpg	VERTICAL FIELD OF VIEW	57
FILE SIZE (kB)	<1 kB	SHUTTER TIME	1

You can modify the Comment field if you press the Modify button on the toolbar. To save or interrupt the modification process, you should use Save or Cancel button on the bottom of the Inspection Data Details panel.